

The Impact of Financial Development and Renewable Energy Consumption on Carbon Emissions: An Empirical Analysis for Türkiye

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Abstract

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The primary objective of this paper is to conduct empirical research examining the influence of financial development and the utilization of renewable energy on carbon emissions within the context of Türkiye. In the paper, the period of 1990-2019 was examined. In the paper, four different regression models have been established in which total carbon emissions and per capita carbon emissions are the dependent variables, and Renewable energy consumption, along with the comprehensive characterization of currency encompassing the broader monetary aggregates, signifying financial development, is employed as the independent variable within the analysis. Moreover, the incremental value stemming from industrialization is incorporated as a controlled parameter in the statistical models. The data utilized for this study were procured from the World Bank. The models formulated within the study's ambit were estimated by the least squares method. As a result of the estimation of the models, it was identified that the impact of financial development on carbon emissions was statistically significant and positive. It has been determined that utilization of sustainable energy sources is statistically proven to have a significant and negative effects on carbon emissions. It has been concluded that the added value arising from industrialization, which is considered as a control variable, is statistically significant and positive on carbon emission variables.

Finansal Gelişme ve Yenilenebilir Enerji Tüketiminin Karbon Salınımına Etkisi: Türkiye İçin Ampirik Bir Analiz

Öz

Key Words:

Finansal
Gelişme,
Karbon
Emisyonu,
Yenilenebilir
Enerji

Bu çalışmanın amacı, Türkiye'de karbon salınımında finansal gelişme ve yenilenebilir enerji tüketiminin rolünün ampirik olarak araştırılmasıdır. Çalışmada 1990-2019 dönemi incelenmiştir. Çalışmada toplam karbon emisyonunun ve kişi başına düşen karbon emisyonlarının bağımlı değişken, yenilenebilir enerji tüketimi ve finansal gelişme göstergesi olan geniş para tanımının bağımsız değişken olduğu dört farklı regresyon modeli kurulmuştur. Ayrıca modellerde sanayileşmeden kaynaklanan katma değer ise kontrol değişkeni olarak ele alınmıştır. Çalışmanın verileri, Dünya Bankası'ndan elde edilmiştir. Çalışma kapsamında geliştirilen modeller en küçük kareler yöntemiyle tahmin edilmiştir. Modellerin tahmin sonucunda finansal gelişmenin karbon emisyonu üzerinde etkisinin istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve pozitif yönlü olduğu saptanmıştır. Yenilenebilir enerji tüketiminin ise karbon emisyonu üzerindeki etkisinin istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve negatif yönlü olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Kontrol değişkeni olarak ele alınan sanayileşmeden kaynaklanan katma değer ise karbon emisyonu değişkenleri üzerinde istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve pozitif yönlü olduğu sonucuna varılmıştır.

INTRODUCTION

Energy, defined as the ability to do work, has been humanity's greatest need since its existence. Today, the need for energy has increased day by day because of the fast rise in the world population, industrialization, etc.

Energy resources are divided into non-renewable energy and renewable energy. Energy resources that cannot be recycled once used are called non-renewable energy resources. Non-renewable energy is also referred to by names such as primary, conventional and exhaustible energy resources in the literature. Non-renewable energy resources, coal, natural gas, oil, etc. consists of elements. Experts predict that non-renewable energy resources that can exist with reserve discoveries will be exhausted within a few centuries. Harmful emissions, especially CO₂, are released by the utilization of finite energy reserves. These emissions harm all living things in the world. In addition, the greenhouse gas effect created by the emissions released on our world causes global warming and brings much negativity such as climate changes (Kademli, 2020). With the outbreak of the energy crisis in 1973, the inadequacy of non-renewable energy sources and the destruction they caused in the world were observed, and research on renewable energy resources gained momentum (Öztürk, 2013).

Renewable energy resources are natural, recyclable and environmentally friendly energy resources. They can be used in homes, workplaces and heating-cooling systems, in short, wherever non-renewable energy sources are used. Wind energy, solar energy, hydraulic energy, geothermal energy, biomass energy are renewable energy resources (Yarımkaya, 2021).

Developments in technology, industrialization, and increasing population have undoubtedly caused an rise in energy supply. The search for more energy, which continued with the oil crisis after the industrial revolution, is obtained from fossil fuels, which are our primary energy provider even today. This situation causes the rapid depletion of fossil fuels and the increase in their emissions. Undoubtedly, after this point, the industry will progress further and the energy supply will increase in parallel. In our world, which is warming under the effect of greenhouse gases, climates are changing and irreversible damages are in question. For these reasons, we need energy sources that are environmentally friendly, renewable, accessible and capable of endless energy. The biggest obstacle to the utilize renewable energy resources is the presence fossil fuel systems that have been used for years. It is known that sustainable and environmentally friendly energy reserves used together with fossil fuels cause a decrease in emission rates. In this way, the industry can shift towards sustainable and replenish able energy reserves in stages. In particular, the establishment of new systems to be established with government incentives with renewable energy sources will allow us to reduce the emission rate over time and make the world more livable. In this respect, it is very important that finance providers such as government incentives and bank loans, support renewable energy sources (Doğanay & Coşkun, 2020).

After the energy crisis, negative environmental impacts from the utilize fossil fuels have also been revealed, and countries have increased their initiatives in this regard. For decrease the CO₂ emission caused by the use of fossil fuels, countries have come together with activities such as the Kyoto Protocol and the Rio conference have taken steps for a clean world. Türkiye has attended in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, the Paris Agreement and the Kyoto Protocol.

Although our land has large coal resources, the poor quality and insufficiency of the coal makes our country dependent on foreign energy. Being foreign-dependent on energy, which is the most important input of the industry, is one of the biggest obstacles to the progress of the country's economy. Although our developing country is insufficient in terms of fossil fuels, it is wealthy in renewable energy resources. It is rich in renewable energy resources such as abundant water resources, high number of sunny days, wind, dense vegetation and forests. Our country also benefits from renewable energy sources, especially hydroelectricity, but it should undoubtedly be improved. It is clear that the acceleration of the steps taken regarding renewable energy sources will improve the economy, environment and welfare in our country, which imports 70 percent of the energy (Öztürk, 2013).

While of the effect utilizing renewable energy on carbon emissions is among the topics discussed in the literature, the determinants of financing investments in expanding and promoting the consumptive of renewable energy sources are also amongst the issues examined. With regard to providing financing, the issue of financial development of countries comes to the fore.

Within the scope of the above knowledge, the aims of this investigative is to examine the influence of financial advancement and the utilization of sustainable energy on carbon emissions between 1990-2019 in Türkiye. In the next part of the introductory part of the study planned for this purpose, there is a literature review on the subject. In the methodology section that follows, the dataset and analytical framework employed in this investigation are introduced and the observations are mentioned. Finally, the study was concluded with conclusions and recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous studies in the literature, it seems like that the relationship of carbon emission with energy exhaustion, renewable energy exhaustion and different macroeconomic and financial variables is discussed in terms of different country groups. In this context, some of the studies in the literature are given below.

Erdoğan and Ganiev (2016) investigated the link among CO₂ emissions examined, economic development, energy use, and financial openness in Central Asian countries. The authors used panel data analysis by examining the years 1992-2013 in the paper. In conclusion, they determined the existence of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC).

Bora and Atasoy (2018) examined the correlation among financial progress and carbon emissions within the G7 nations. They accepted financial development as the criteria of domestic credit volume and carbon emission per capita as a measure of environmental degradation, and carried out their studies in accordance with the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) theory. As a result of their studies, they determined that the rise in financial development and energy expenditure increases carbon emissions. They also found that a 1% rise in energy expenditure increases per capita carbon emissions by 0.9%.

Çetin and Bakırtaş (2018) explored the correlation between financial progress and the use of renewable energy within the scope of G7 countries. They carried out the research between 1991 and 2011. They found that there is a long-term relation among the factor discussed in the study.

Çetin and Yüksel (2018) analyzed the association between the Turkish economy and environmental impact. In the study, they used data between 1960 and 2014. Stability analysis was performed with Ng-Perron and PP tests, and the existence of cointegration was performed with Johansen-Juselius and Philips-Quliaris tests. Based on results of the statistical tests, the variables exhibit stationarity and cointegrated at first difference. In the empirical results, they determined that energy consumption increases carbon emissions. In addition, in the study, they examined the EKC hypothesis and concluded that the hypothesis was supported for Türkiye.

In a study by Pata (2018), an examination was carried out on the short- and long-term dynamic interconnection among GDP per capita, per capita carbon dioxide emissions, financial development, total renewable energy consumption per capita, hydroelectric consumption, alternative energy consumption, and urbanization spanning the years from 1974 to 2014. The author used ARDL bounds test approximation, Gregory-Hansen and Hatemi-J cointegration tests in the study. As a result of the cointegration tests, the author revealed indicating the existence of a sustained relationship between the variables over an extended period. The findings revealed that as economic growth, financial development, and urbanization progress, there is a concurrent increase in environmental degradation. On the other hand, total renewable energy expenditure, hydroelectric expenditure, and alternative energy expenditure were not found to exert a notable influence on CO₂ emissions. In addition, Pata found that economic progress provided the largest increase in CO₂ emissions, sequenced by urbanization and financial advancement.

Pata and Yurtkuran (2018) investigated the compatibility of the Turkish economy with the EKC hypothesis between 1981 and 2014. In the study conducted with the ARDL limit test method, they found that the validity of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis was approved. In the work, they concluded that settlements where population density is kept at appropriate levels will be effective in reducing carbon dioxide emissions.

Güvercin (2019) examined the correlation involving financial progress and carbon emissions with the GMM approach. This investigation encompassed 52 nations, employing the economic model determined with the data between 2001-2014. Consequently, the work uncovered that there is an EKC, and that the urban population and electricity utilization exhibits a positive impact on carbon emissions.

Altınöz and Altuntaş (2020) investigated the role of tourism, renewable energy expenditure, financial development, trade and total energy expenditure in carbon emissions pertaining to G20 countries. In light of the study's findings, they determined that energy expenditure rise carbon dioxide emissions, while the increase in renewable energy and tourism revenues reduces carbon dioxide emissions. On the other hand, they did not observe a noteworthy impact concerning financial progress.

Şit and Hacıevliyağil (2020) investigated the effects of energy expenditure on financial progress in Türkiye. In their study, they examined electricity expenditure, carbon emissions and energy imports in Türkiye between 1970 and 2015 by using ARDL limit test approach. Regarding their research, they determined that energy imports have a significant and positive effect on bank loans in the short start.

In his study, Karasoy (2021) examined the ecological implications of economic globalization and financial advancement in Türkiye. Conducted this investigation with the extended distributed lagged autoregressive (extended ARDL) bounds test approach between 1980 and 2016. As a result of his research, he determined that long-term analysis indicated that economic and financial globalization did not exert a notable influence on carbon dioxide emissions in Türkiye, while commercial globalization reduced carbon dioxide emissions.

Namahoro, Wu, Zhou, and Xue (2021) empirically examine the sustained influence of energy density, renewable energy utilization, and economic expansion on CO₂ emissions against various regions and income levels in over 50 African nations from 1980 to 2018. Panel data analysis, causal analysis and decomposition of variance were utilized in the study. Results obtained from panel estimations revealed that, at various income levels and in different regions, higher renewable energy consumption was linked with a decrease in CO₂ emissions. Conversely, an rise in energy intensity was linked to a rise in emissions and in Africa. They found that causality testing confirmed bidirectional between CO₂ emissions and determining factors in Africa, accounting for diverse regional contexts and income levels.

Pala and Barut (2021) explored the ramifications of financial advancement, economic expansion, and energy utilization on ecological well-being within the economies of E-7 nations. They carried out their studies with panel data analysis, utilizing data spanning from 1990 to 2014. They found that carbon emissions increased with economic growth for Türkiye and Russia, resulting in a reduce in environmental class.

In his study, Yılmaz (2021) examined the relation among financial improving, economic growing and renewable energy expenditure of G7 countries by means of panel causality test. In the study, the author examined the years 1980-2018. As a result of the research, an asymmetric interaction was found in the relation among financial improving and renewable energy expenditure.

Zeren and Karaca (2021) examined the relation among renewable-non-renewable energy expenditure and financial growing in developing countries. They carried out their studies with data between 1980-2018. They considered the ratio of deposits in banks to GDP and the ratio of financial system deposits to GDP as indicators of financial development. According to the panel cointegration tests they applied, they determined that a positive association was identified between the utilization of renewable energy and financial development. They establish a one-way causality among non-renewable energy and financial growing.

Afşar and Yüksel (2022) investigated the asymmetric relationship of carbon emissions in Türkiye on economic globalization and financial development. They used NARDL (Non-linear lag distributed autoregressive model) in the study. As a result of the work, they decided that globalization increases carbon emissions in the long and short term. Besides, in the Wald test results in terms of asymmetry, they obtained short-term results in terms of fiscal growing and long-term results in terms of globalization.

Akram, Umar, Xiaoli, and Chen (2022) examined the influence of energy efficiency, adoption of renewable energy, and various determinants on carbon emissions in Mexico, Indonesia, Nigeria, and Türkiye (MINT). In the work, the authors demonstrated the asymmetric link between energy efficiency, renewable energy, nuclear energy, economic growing and CO₂ emissions in MINT countries usage the data from 1990-2014 and the employing a novel concealed panel cointegration technique and a non-linear panel autoregressive distribution lag methodology. Based on their empirical findings, they found that the impact of variables are asymmetrical and that energy yield and renewable energy mitigate carbon emissions in MINT nations.

Awan, Abbasi, Rej, Bandyopadhyay, and Lv (2022) examined the relation between renewable energy, the act of foreign direct investor, environmental problems and urbanization in 10 growing countries between 1996 and 2015. The Moments Quantile Regression Method was used for the analysis. In their study, they determined the presence of the Environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis. Besides, they found that while foreign direct investor was important and positive in 0.05-0.50 tranches, it became meaningless in higher tranches. They found that as urbanization develops, renewable energy reduces carbon dioxide emissions at all quantitative levels, while knowledge connection technology represented by internet use significantly to reduce environmental corruption at 0.25-0.95th quintile levels.

Ecevit and Çetin (2022) examined the impacts of economic progress, sustainable energy expenditure, financial advancement and urbanization on healthcare expenses in Türkiye. In the work, ADF, PP, DF-GLS, Johansen-Juselius, ARDL and VECM tests were applied with the data between 1985-2018. As a result, they found that Cointegration was established among the variables, indicating a long-term relationship. Moreover, the study revealed that both the utilization of renewable energy and financial advancement exhibited an adverse influence on health expenditures, whereas economic expansion showed a favorable impact on healthcare costs. They found that In the long term, a mutually causal relationship was identified among health spending, expenditure of renewable energy, financial improving, and urbanization.

Efeoğlu (2022) investigated the effects of renewable energy, energy usage, industrialization and financial advancement on carbon dioxide emissions in E7 nations. The study was carried out using the Environmental Kuznets Curve between 1989 and 2016. Estimation of the model was conducted employing the Parks-Kmenta estimator approach. The work revealed that the EKC hypothesis is suitable and the GDP, industrialization and energy consumption in the E7 countries increase the CO₂ emissions. In addition, in his study, he suggested investing in renewable energy sources in order to reduce CO₂ emissions.

Ehigiamusoe and Doğan (2022) examined the impacts of renewable energy consumption on carbon emissions in low-income countries. As a result of the study, they determined that renewable energy expenditure, decreases carbon emissions.

Haldar and Sethi (2022) investigated the prompt impacts of information and communication technologies (ICT) on the environment, as well as the interactions involving renewable energy, trade, and financial development, utilizing Driscoll-Kraay Panel Adjusted Estimators for a set of 16 developing nations spanning the period from 2000 to 2018. They found that increasing internet use, renewable energy consumption and trade significantly decreases CO₂ emissions, conversely, an escalation in non-renewable energy consumption markedly amplifies CO₂ emissions.

In their work, İlarıslan and Yıldız (2022) investigated the effects of financial improving and foreign direct investments on renewable energy in Asia-Pacific and Latin American countries between 2000 and 2020. Dumitrescu-Hurlin panel causality test and simultaneous panel quantile regression analysis were used in the study. They found that financial development and foreign direct investment have a positive and significant effect on renewable energy production.

In their work, İskenderoğlu, Ünlübulduk and Karadeniz (2022) investigated, the impact of foreign direct investment, economic expansion, financial advancement, and the adoption of renewable energy on carbon emissions. using panel data analysis. The study covers 14 nations involved in the Environmental Performance Index. The authors discussed the period of 1990-2018 in the study. As a result of the research, concluded that economic growth, inflow of foreign direct investment, and utilization of renewable energy exhibit a detrimental impact on carbon emissions.

Nakhli, Shahbaz, Jebli, and Wang (2022) examined the relation among renewable and non-renewable electricity expenditure, carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, and economic policy ambiguity for the United States. They carried out the empirical work with the Bootstrap Rolling approach with monthly data up to 1985M1-2020M12. In their empirical findings, they concluded that in the comprehensive sample, the Granger causality test indicated a one-way causal relationship from electricity consumption to economic policy uncertainty, and a reciprocal causal connection between CO₂ emissions and economic policy uncertainty.

Polat and Kızıllkan (2022) investigated the relation among renewable energy expenditure per capita, carbon emissions due to energy expenditure, and GDP, using the data among 1990 and 2012 in Türkiye. As a result of the regression

analysis they carried out, the carbon emission of the renewable energy expenditure per capita negatively; They found that increases in GDP have a positive impact on carbon emissions per capita.

Sun, Li, Andlib, and Genie (2022) examined the relation among renewable energy expenditure, urbanization, economic growing and carbon emissions in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. They used data from 1991 to 2019 in their studies. In their work, they saw the presence of the Environmental Kuznets Curve theory. They also found that rapid urbanization and economic progress cause higher carbon emissions, whereas the integration of renewable energy is associated with a reduce in carbon emissions.

Topçu (2022) investigated, the impacts of renewable and non-renewable energy expenditure and natural resource revenues on carbon emissions in Türkiye between 1990-2015 using ARDL, FMOLS and CCR models. In the first model, he determined that the effect of financial improving on carbon emissions is positive, while the effect of renewable energy and natural resource revenues on carbon emissions is negative. In his second model, he determined that the effect of non-renewable energy expenditure on carbon emissions is positive.

Kavas and Çoban (2023) examined the effect of financial development on renewable energy expenditure in CIVETS (Colombia, Indonesia, Vietnam, Egypt, Türkiye, South Africa) countries. They carried out their studies using data between 1990-2019. They used utilized renewable energy as the dependent variant and the financial progress indicator as the independent variable. They used the Non-Additive Fixed Effect Panel Quantile method in their analysis. In light of the study, it was observed that financial improving has an adverse impact on renewable energy consumption across all quantile levels in CIVETS nations.

Şahin (2023) examined the influence renewable energy growth in Türkiye on financial growth among the years 1990-2020. The work was carried out with the financial development index. As a consequence of the research, a A substantial and reverse correlation was founded among financial growth and renewable energy.

Yıldız (2023) examined the nexus between economic progress and financial advancement and carbon neutrality in Türkiye. The author carried out his work using the ARDL test among 1980 and 2020. Consequence, it has been defined that both the economic growth and financial growing of Türkiye are obstacles to achieving the aim of carbon neutrality in 2050.

In the work conducted by Adebayo, Awosusi, Rjoub, Agyekum and Kirikkaleli (2022), the impact of globalization and renewable energy use on consumption-based carbon emissions in MINT countries among 1990 and 2018 was researched. However, the function of non-renewable energy use and economic growing has also been empirically examined. Second generation cointegration tests were used in the study. Following the conducted tests, they ascertained the presence of a sustained nexus among the variables. They also found that economic growth and energy use in the respective countries drive carbon emissions. As a result of the study, they also emphasized that globalization and the utilize of renewable energy help decrease ecological corruption.

When the works in the literature are investigated, it has been seen that economic and financial indicators are related and effective in the carbon emission of countries in general. In addition, energy usage and the effect of sustainable energy spending on carbon emissions have been frequently discussed in the literature. It is possible to state that the study differs from other works in the literature because the role of financial improving and renewable energy expenditure in carbon emissions is researched in detail with four different econometric models.

METHODOLOGY

This work researches the influence of financial development and the utilization of renewable energy on carbon emissions. in Türkiye between 1990 and 2019 has been investigated using the method of least squares.

This section provides detailed information regarding the dataset, methodologies, and outcomes of the investigation.

Data of the Study

Table 1 presents the symbols, descriptions, measurement units, and details regarding the data sources of the variables included in the paper.

Table 1: Variables

Symbol of Variable	Description	Unit of Measurement	Source of Data
CO ₂₁	Carbon emission	Kiloton	The World Bank
CO ₂₂	Carbon emissions per capita	Metric Ton	The World Bank
BROAD	Broad definition of money (ratio to GDP)	%	The World Bank
RE	Renewable energy consumption (ratio to total final energy consumption)	%	The World Bank
INDUSTRY	Added value based on industry	\$	The World Bank

When examining Table 1, it can be observed that there are two different variables related to carbon emissions: total carbon emissions and per capita carbon emissions. The reason for this is to aim for a detailed analysis of the role of carbon emissions in financial development and the consumption of renewable energy sources. The variables representing carbon emissions for CO₂₁ and CO₂₂ encompass the carbon dioxide emitted during the consumption of solid, liquid, and gaseous fuels, as well as carbon dioxide resulting from gas flaring. In the study, the variable representing the financial development indicator, BROAD, represents the broad money definition, which refers to the total currency in circulation excluding banks. The variable representing RE, on the other hand, represents the share of renewable energy in total final energy consumption. The variable representing INDUSTRY represents the value added in the mining, manufacturing, construction, and electricity, water, and gas sectors.

The data included in the study are annual and cover the period from 1990 to 2019.

Models of the Study

In the research of the influence of financial advancement and the utilization of sustainable energy on carbon emissions, four different regression models have been developed. These models are presented below.

$$CO_{21t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 BROAD_t + \beta_2 INDUSTRY_t + u_t \quad (1)$$

$$CO_{22t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 BROAD_t + \beta_2 INDUSTRY_t + u_t \quad (2)$$

$$CO_{21t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 RE_t + \beta_2 INDUSTRY_t + u_t \quad (3)$$

$$CO_{22t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 RE_t + \beta_2 INDUSTRY_t + u_t \quad (4)$$

In the models, the variables CO₂₁ and CO₂₂ are included as dependent variables. The constant term α and coefficients β_1 and β_2 represent the variables. The subscripted letter t represents the years, while u represents the error term. The variable, BROAD represents financial development as an independent variable in models (1) and (2). The variable RE represents renewable energy consumption as an independent variable in models (3) and (4). The variable INDUSTRY, representing industrialization, is included as a control variable in all models.

Findings

Under this heading, the study presents descriptive statistical details regarding the variables, results of unit root tests, and findings related to the assumptions and predictions of the models.

Table 2 presents descriptive statistical information about the variables included in the paper.

Table 2: Introductory Statistics

Variable	Number of Observations	Average	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
CO ₂₁	30	255158	85171.28	139197.9	415898.2

LNCO ₂₁	30	12.3951	0.3375	11.8436	12.9382
CO ₂₂	30	3.6300	0.7624	2.5623	5.0663
LNCO ₂₂	30	1.2679	0.2104	0.9409	1.6226
BROAD	30	0.4133	0.1037	0.2374	0.5874
RE	30	0.1700	0.0453	0.1140	0.2451
INDUSTRY	30	1.36e+11	8.22e+10	4.19e+10	2.65e+11
LNINDUSTRY	30	25.435	0.669	24.459	26.303

When examining Table 2, it can be observed that it offers the count of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values for the variables considered in the research. It is noted that the number of observations for all variables is 30. Therefore, it can be inferred that there is no missing data for the period of 1990-2019 covered in the study. Considering the substantial differences in the minimum and maximum values among the variables CO₂₁, CO₂₂, and INDUSTRY in the study, their natural logarithms were taken to mitigate the scale disparity. In light of these findings, the models of the study were reconfigured as follows:

$$\text{LNCO}_{21t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 \text{BROAD}_t + \beta_2 \text{LNINDUSTRY}_t + u_t \quad (1.1)$$

$$\text{LNCO}_{22t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 \text{BROAD}_t + \beta_2 \text{LNINDUSTRY}_t + u_t \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{LNCO}_{21t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 \text{RE}_t + \beta_2 \text{LNINDUSTRY}_t + u_t \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{LNCO}_{22t} = \alpha_t + \beta_1 \text{RE}_t + \beta_2 \text{LNINDUSTRY}_t + u_t \quad (4.1)$$

In the study, the stationarity tests for the variables were conducted using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Philips-Perron (PP) unit root tests, and the findings are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Philips-Perron (PP) Unit Root Tests

Variables	Extended Dickey-Fuller (ADF)		Philips-Perron (PP)	
	Fixed	Fixed-Trend	Fixed	Fixed-Trend
LNCO₂₁	-0.737	-3.463***	-0.897	-3.173
ΔLNCO₂₁	-5.720*	-5.617*	-8.309*	-8.125*
LNCO₂₂	-0.832	-3.422***	-0.728	-3.283***
ΔLNCO₂₂	-5.801*	-5.682*	-8.392*	-8.049*
BROAD	-0.762	-4.107	-0.841	-4.047**
ΔBROAD	-7.866*	-7.695*	-20.436*	-19.798*
RE	-1.579	-1.313	-1.603	-0.820
ΔRE	-5.173*	-5.754*	-5.828*	-6.816*
LNINDUSTRY	-0.989	-1.775	-0.989	-1.871
ΔLNINDUSTRY	-5.238*	-5.186*	-5.238*	-5.187*

Note: *, **, and *** represent the significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Δ: First Difference.

Upon examining Table 3, it can be observed that the variables LNCO₂₁, LNCO₂₂, BROAD, RE, and LNINDUSTRY included in the study are stationary state in their first difference, denoted as I(1). Accordingly, in the estimation of the models, the first difference values of the variables were used instead of their level values.

In the study, the models were estimated using the Prais-Winsten transformation and the method of least squares. The results of tests regarding the estimation of the models and the assumptions of the estimators are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Least Squares Method (Prais-Winsten Transformation)

Model/ Variables	(1.1)	(2.1)	(3.1)	(4.1)
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ΔBROAD	0.8979*	0.5040*		
	(0.2298)	(0.1775)		
ΔRE			-4.1085*	-2.8963*
			(0.7066)	(0.4817)
ΔLNINDUSTRY	0.3597*	0.2343*	0.1856*	0.1119*
	(0.0398)	(0.0285)	(0.0499)	(0.0340)
Fixed Term	2.8732	-4.9006*	8.3715*	-1.0822
	(0.9668)	(0.6743)	(1.3596)	(0.9263)
R²	0.9952	0.8771	0.9974	0.8663
F test	2667.42*	92.81*	4909.22*	84.20*
White Test(p)	0.2969	0.3844	0.0518	0.1904
Durbin Watson	0.8751	1.2488	0.3854	0.5036
Breush Godfrey LM	0.0058	0.0897	0.000	0.0001
Jarque-Bera Test	0.3919	0.351	0.3821	0.2393
Average VIF	4.16	4.16	6.83	6.83

Note 1: * indicates significance at the 1% level.

Note2: The values within parentheses represent standard errors.

Table 4 presents the estimation results of the models using the least squares method and the results of tests related to the assumptions of the method. Prior to model estimation, a test for multicollinearity was conducted. The variance inflation factor (VIF) was examined as it is one of the commonly used criteria for detecting multicollinearity issues, by assessing the average VIF values of the variables included in the models. According to Yerdelen-Tatoğlu (2020), a VIF value between 0 and 5 indicates the absence of multicollinearity, a value between 5 and 10 suggests moderate multicollinearity, and a value greater than 10 indicates strong multicollinearity. In models (1.1) and (2.1), the VIF values were calculated as 4.16, while in models (3.1) and (4.1), the VIF values were computed as 6.83. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is multicollinearity in models (1.1) and (2.1), and moderate multicollinearity in models (3.1) and (4.1). In this context, it has been concluded that there is no significant issue of multicollinearity in any of the four models constructed in the study. Secondly, the problem of heteroscedasticity was examined using the White test. The probability values obtained from the White test for all models indicate the absence of heteroscedasticity. Thirdly, existence of autocorrelation in the models was examined by the Durbin Watson and Breusch Godfrey LM tests. The results obtained from the Durbin Watson test indicate the presence of autocorrelation in all models. Additionally, the results of the Breusch Godfrey Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test also support the presence of autocorrelation in the model. Lastly, the normality of the models was investigated using the Jarque-Bera test, and it was determined that the models exhibit normal distribution. Consequently, it was found that there are no issues of multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, or non-normal distribution in the models, but there is a presence of autocorrelation. To address the issue of autocorrelation, the Prais-Winsten transformation was applied to the models.

The four models developed in the study were estimated using the Prais-Winsten transformation and the method of least squares. The results of the F-test, indicating the overall significance of the model, demonstrate that all models are significant at the 1% level. The R-squared values, representing the explanatory power of the models, are above 85% for all models. Furthermore, the findings obtained from the model estimation reveal that the variable INDUSTRY, which is included as a control variable, has a statistically considerable and favorable impact on the variables CO₂₁ and CO₂₂ in all models.

According to the results in Table 4, upon examining the estimation results of models (1.1) and (2.1), it can be observed that the independent variables have a significant and positive effect on the dependent variables at the 1% level. To elaborate further, as indicated by the outcomes of the model (1.1), a 1% increase in the BROAD variable leads to a 0.89% increase in the CO₂₁ variable. According to the estimation results of model (2.1), a 1% increase in the BROAD variable manifest as a 0.50% increase in the CO₂₂ variable. In other words, an increase in the ratio of broad money supply within the GDP can lead to an increase in both total carbon emissions and per capita carbon emissions.

Upon examining the estimation results of models (3.1) and (4.1), it can be observed that the independent variables have a significant and negative effect on the dependent variables at the 1% level. In detail, based on the results of model (3.1), a 1% increase in the RE variable leads to an approximate 4.10% reduction in the CO₂₁ variable. According to the results of model (4.1), a 1% increase in the RE variable result in an approximate 2.89% reduction in the CO₂₂ variable. In other

words, an increase in the percentage of energy consumption from renewable sources in total final energy consumption can reduce both total carbon emissions and per capita carbon emissions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In this paper, the empirical act of financial development and renewable energy consumption in carbon emissions in Türkiye between 1990 and 2019 has been investigated. Four different models were developed and estimated using the least squares method. In the models, variables related to carbon emissions were treated as dependent variables, while variables concerned to financial development and renewable energy consumption were considered as independent variables. The value added based on industrial activities was used as a control variable.

The study utilizes two variables, namely total carbon emissions and per capita carbon emissions, to represent carbon emissions. The purpose is to provide a detailed analysis of carbon emissions in relation to the variables under consideration. The share of broad money in GDP represents financial development. As for renewable energy consumption, the variable used is the share of renewable energy consumption in total energy consumption. The data for these variables were acquired from the World Bank.

In order to address the detected issue of autocorrelation in the estimation of the developed models, the Prais-Winsten transformation was utilized. The estimation results of the first and second models, using the Prais-Winsten transformation and the method of least squares, revealed that an rise in the share of broad money supply within GDP can potentially lead to an increase in carbon emissions. For this reason, considering the share of broad money supply within GDP as a measure of financial development in the study, it can be concluded that an rise in the level of financial development is associated with an rise in carbon emissions.

In the estimation of the third and fourth models using the Prais-Winsten transformation and the method of least squares, it was found that an rise in the share of renewable energy consumption in total energy consumption can potentially lead to a reduction in carbon emissions. In this context, it can be concluded that an rise in renewable energy consumption contributes to a decrease in carbon emissions. Additionally, the findings across all models indicate that an increase in value added based on industrial activities is related to a rise in carbon emissions. These empirical findings align with the study conducted by Topçu (2022).

In conclusion, regarding the data analysis, it is evident that an increase in the degree of financial advancement in Türkiye between 1990 and 2019 may contribute to an increase in carbon emissions, while an rise in renewable energy consumption can potentially lead to a decrease in carbon emissions. However, this does not imply that the level or pace of financial development should be reduced in terms of environmental practices. In this context, it is recommended to prioritize environmental considerations in policies focused on augmenting the degree of financial development in Türkiye. Furthermore, the findings from the study hold significance in terms of raising awareness and developing policies related to the use of renewable energy sources.

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